

TABLE 1—INDIRECT DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH STANDARD (0.05 N) HYDRATED COPPER (II) PERCHLORATE IN ACETONITRILE

Mercaptans	Amount found**†, mg		Amount found***,mg	
2-Mercaptoethanol	4.05	0.026	12.12	0.042
Isobutyl mercaptan	3.96	0.031	12.10	0.042
n-Butyl mercaptan	4.03	0.036	12.10	0.046
Benzyl mercaptan	3.98	0.029	11.87	0.058
Dodecyl mercaptan	4.00	0.041	12.13	0.049
Thiophenol	4.05	0.031	12.02	0.038
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	3.96	0.042	12.13	0.047

* Amount taken, 4 mg

** Amount taken, 12 mg

† Mean of ten determinations with standard deviation (\pm)

Results and Discussion :

The oxidations involving copper(II) as an oxidant in aqueous medium has not gained much importance due to the instability and air-oxidation of the resulting copper(I). The use of copper(II) in acetonitrile has the advantage that copper(I) is stabilised as acetonitrile complex and hence there is little risk of air oxidation. Because of the stabilisation of copper(I) relative to copper(II), the potential copper(II)–(I) couple is increased markedly¹⁰ and this makes copper(II) as a powerful oxidising agent in acetonitrile.

The results indicate that one mole of mercaptan requires one equivalent of copper(II). This corresponds to the oxidation of mercapto group to the disulphide. The overall standard deviation

(Table 1) calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 4 mg of each mercaptan is 0.034. The same for 12-mg sample is 0.045. It may be mentioned here that the residual copper(II) may be titrated potentiometrically using a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified-calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode. A sharp drop in potential is observed at the equivalence point in each potentiometric titration.

Because of their importance in biological systems, the determination of mercaptans is of great value. The compounds are quite susceptible to oxidation but much less soluble in water. The application of non-aqueous oxidimetric methods to the determination of mercaptans is therefore of great interest and scope.

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Oxidation of Some Sugars with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV) in Nitric Acid Medium

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VARIOUS oxidimetric methods are available for the determination of sugars¹⁻⁶. In the present work a quick and convenient method has been developed for the milligram determination of some mono and disaccharides. The sugar sample was allowed to react with excess of Ce(IV) reagent at room temperature (25°) and the unreacted Ce(IV) reagent was titrated against Fe(II) using ferroin indicator.

The present method is superior to many other methods in accuracy, quickness and reproducibility. The oxidising reagent is fairly stable and gives clear and sharp end point within the accuracy of $\pm 1\%$.

Experimental

0.15N Ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution (A. R., B. D. H.): 20g of ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) was exactly weighed and dissolved in 8.3 ml of 15 N nitric acid and made up to the mark in a 250 ml flask with distilled water. The solution was standardised by titration with 0.025 N aqueous solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin (0.001 M solution) on indicator.

The stock solutions of sugars (AR, BDH) were prepared by dissolving the accurately weighed amount of the sample in distilled water.

Procedure: Aliquots containing 2-10 mg of the sample were introduced in a 100 ml iodine flask and 5 ml of 0.15 N ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution was added to it. The flask was stoppered and the contents shaken well. The reaction mixture was allowed to react for 40 (monosaccharides) to 70 (disaccharides) minutes at room temperature. After

the reaction was over, the stopper was rinsed with 5 ml distilled water and 10 ml of 1*N* sulphuric acid was added. The contents were shaken for a minute and the unreacted Ce(IV) was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions and the recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the titre values of the blank and the actual experiment.

as the final reaction products. On the basis of stoichiometry and the identification of final oxidation products we conclude the same reaction path as reported earlier⁶.

TABLE—DETERMINATION OF SOME SUGARS WITH THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sample	Sample taken (mg)	Actual Equivalents of Ce(IV) consumed/mole of the sample	Sugars found (mg) by calculation	Error %
1. Xylose	2.5000	10	2.5200	+0.80
	5.0000	10	5.0500	+1.00
	7.5000	10	7.5700	+0.93
2. Glucose	2.5000	12	2.5200	+0.80
	5.0000	12	5.0600	+1.20
	7.5000	12	7.5800	+1.06
3. Galactose	2.5000	12	2.5300	+1.20
	5.0000	12	5.0500	+1.00
	7.5000	12	7.5600	+0.80
4. Fructose	3.5000	14	3.5350	+1.00
	7.0000	14	7.0600	+0.85
	10.5000	14	10.6000	+0.94
5. Sorbose	3.5000	14	3.5420	+1.20
	7.0000	14	7.0600	+0.85
	10.5000	14	10.6000	+0.95
6. Maltose	2.2000	26	2.1800	-0.90
	4.4000	26	4.3500	-1.13
	8.8000	26	8.8900	+1.02
7. Lactose	2.5000	26	2.4800	-0.80
	5.0000	26	4.9500	-1.00
	7.5000	26	7.4200	-1.06
8. Sucrose	2.5000	26	2.4800	-0.80
	5.0000	26	4.9400	-1.20
	7.5000	26	7.4300	-0.93

Discussion

The effect of the concentration of nitric acid, temperature, the amount of Ce(IV) reagent and the reaction time was studied. Boiling of the reaction mixture even for 40-60 minutes does not bring any change in the speed of the reaction and the recovery of the sample. Inconvenience is noticed in observing the end point.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was also established and the final oxidation products were identified. It was found that the aldoses give formic acid as the final oxidation product, while ketoses evolve carbon dioxide in addition to formic acid. Disaccharides also give formic acid and carbon dioxide

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Complexing Equilibria Involved Between Hafnium and Bromopyrogallol Red and Nitroso R Salt in Aqueous Solution

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THE quantitative equilibria involved between Hf(IV) and *o*-(2, 7-dibromo-4, 5, 6-trihydroxy-3-oxo-3H-xanthen-9-yl) benzene sulphonic acid (Bromopyrogallol Red, i. e. BPGR) and 3-hydroxy-4-nitroso 2,7-naphthalene disulphonic acid (Nitroso R salt, i.e. NRS) in aqueous solution is being reported in this paper. With NRS, however, some potentiometric work⁴ on the nature and stability constants of hafnium complexes have been reported⁵ earlier.

Experimental

Apparatus : Beckman DU-2 Spectrophotometer with glass cells of 1 cm. path length was used. An Elico pH meter model LI-10 was used for pH measurements.

Reagents : Solution of hafnium oxychloride (spec-pure) was prepared by dissolving the sample in a known quantity of HClO₄ in such a way that after dilution the stock solution was 1 × 10⁻³ M in 2M HClO₄ acid. Pure and crystallized samples of BPGR and NRS were used for preparing the stock solutions of the ligands.

Results and Discussion

Acid Dissociation Constants : The *pK* values of the ligands were determined by the method of Albert and Serjeant¹ at room temperature (30°). The *pK*₂, *pK*₃ and *pK*₄ values for BPGR are 5.21, 9.15 and 11.48 whereas *pK*₃ value for NRS is 7.10. The *pK* values relating to the dissociation of sulphonic acid groups